

SWIRRL: Software for Interactive and Reproducible Research Labs

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ABSTRACT

Modern interactive tools for data analysis and visualisation are designed to expose their functionalities as a service through the web. We present in this paper a web API (SWIRRL) that allows Science Gateways to easily integrate such tools in their websites and re-purpose them to their users. The API deals, on behalf of the clients, with the underlying complexity of requesting and organising resources in a target cloud platform hosting the Kubernetes container-orchestration system¹. By combining storage and tools, such as Jupyter notebooks (1) and other visualisation software (2), implemented as containerised services, the API creates dedicated working sessions on-demand. Thanks to the API's workflow functionality, which spawns job executing CWL² workflows for data staging and batch processing, SWIRRL sessions can be populated with raw-data of interest collected from external data providers. Staged data is considered immutable. In the occurrence of updates, older versions are preserved. The system is designed to offer customisation and reproducibility. Notebooks can be further customised with additional or updated libraries, and the provenance of such changes is automatically captured. The recording of provenance is performed for each method of the API's affecting the session. SWIRRL generates and stores provenance data thanks to two dedicated components: the PROV-Template Catalogue³ (3) and the Neo4j database⁴. Both are integrated as microservices and exposed through the API. The ability of collecting provenance is complemented with the possibility of creating snapshots of a running notebook environment. These are stored to Git as Binder⁵ repositories. We will discuss how combining provenance information and

snapshots can be used by SWIRRL to enact different type of reproducibility actions. For instance, to restore the libraries used within an active notebook in the past, or to share and rebuild full Jupyter workspaces, including raw-data and user generated content.

Keywords— *API; Reproducibility; Provenance; Cloud; Notebooks; Collaborative*

Figure 1: SWIRRL Overview

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¹ <https://kubernetes.io/>.

² <https://www.commonwl.org/>.

³ <https://github.com/EnvriPlus-PROV/ProvTemplateCatalog>.

⁴ <https://github.com/neo4j-labs/neo4j-semantic>.

⁵ <https://binderhub.readthedocs.io>.